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Pre-workshop survey & questionnaire form

The survey was conducted between May 15th and 31st, 2018, and it provided material for the early-career researcher (ECR) workshop arranged at the ECCB2018 congress (June 12th to 15th, 2018, in Jyväskylä, Finland). The survey was sent via email to all 140 graduate students registered to the congress through the congress registration database, making use of the fact that graduate students had registered with a lower congress fee. The below message was sent as accompanying the survey link:

Dear Doctoral Students and recently graduated PhDs,

We are arranging a workshop targeted to doctoral students and newly graduated doctors in 5th European Congress of Conservation Biology held during 12th–15th of June 2018 in Jyväskylä, Finland (<https://conbio.org/mini-sites/eccb2018>). The aim of our workshop is to gather young scientists together to discuss about how to transfer the world into more sustainable trajectory. A recent paper concerning the issue is 'World Scientists' Warning to Humanity: A Second Notice' by Ripple et al. 2017 (<https://academic.oup.com/bioscience/article/67/12/1026/4605229>). We are interested to discover which problems and solutions are the most burning ones from the young scientists' point of view. Moreover, we wish to explore whether young researchers have ideas or thoughts not published yet in scientific literature. We will develop a peer reviewed scientific publication based on the workshop discussions. We welcome all workshop participants to become voluntary authors of the paper by contributing to the manuscript. To gather background data for the publication and to derive topics for workshop discussions, we kindly ask you to answer a short questionnaire. Answering is done anonymously and it takes about 5-15 minutes. Participation is voluntary and you can quit the questionnaire at any point. Please respond at the latest in 30th of May.

The link to the survey: <https://link.webpolsurveys.com/S/618F99FF5E1BBC5F>

Workshop: 'The future of conservation science through the eyes of young scientists' on Tuesday, 12th of June at 14-16pm (max 30 participants)

We warmly thank you for answering and welcome all of you to ECCB2018 and to our workshop in Jyväskylä, Finland!

The web survey was created using Webropol 3.0, and it consisted of following questions:

1. Choose your main academic discipline:

[alternatives]

1 = Humanities

2 = Social sciences

3 = Natural sciences

4 = Formal sciences

5 = Professions and applied sciences

6 = Multidisciplinary

2. Please, specify your field of research (e.g. forest ecology, marine biology):

[text field]

3. Year of birth (please write the year in a form yyyy):

[text field]

4. Realised or estimated year of doctoral dissertation (please write the year in a form yyyy):

[text field]

5. Ripple et al. 2017 (<https://academic.oup.com/bioscience/article/67/12/1026/4605229>) introduced 13 steps humanity can take to transition to sustainability. Choose the 3 most important aspects from your perspective:

[multiple choice]

- Prioritising the enactment of connected well-funded and well-managed reserves for a significant proportion of the world's terrestrial, marine, freshwater, and aerial habitats.
- Maintaining nature's ecosystem services by halting the conversion of forests, grasslands, and other native habitats.
- Restoring native plant communities at large scales, particularly forest landscapes.
- Rewilding regions with native species, especially apex predators, to restore ecological processes and dynamics.
- Developing and adopting adequate policy instruments to remedy defaunation, the poaching crisis, and the exploitation and trade of threatened species.
- Reducing food waste through education and better infrastructure.
- Promoting dietary shifts towards mostly plant-based foods.
- Further reducing fertility rates by ensuring that women and men have access to education and voluntary family-planning services, especially where such resources are still lacking.
- Increasing outdoor nature education for children, as well as the overall engagement of society in the appreciation of nature.
- Divesting of monetary investments and purchases to encourage positive environmental change.
- Devising and promoting new green technologies and massively adopting renewable energy sources while phasing out subsidies to energy production through fossil fuels.
- Revising our economy to reduce wealth inequality and ensure that prices, taxation, and incentive systems take into account the real costs which consumption patterns impose on our environment.
- Estimating a scientifically defensible, sustainable human population size for the long term while rallying nations and leaders to support that vital goal.

6. In addition to the list above, and according to your personal perception, what other aspects or study questions scientists should consider in order to achieve a more sustainable world?

[text field]

7. Are you interested in attending the workshop?

[alternatives]

1 = Yes

2 = No

3 = Not sure yet

8. Write here your other possible comments or thoughts for workshop organisers:

[text field]

Note: The organizing team of the workshop (authors 1–7 of the current article) did not themselves answer the survey.

Deriving discussion themes from the pre-workshop survey data

The text answers given to the open-ended questions 6 and 8 were read through and grouped prior to the workshop. The grouping was done independently by author 1 and author 2, and no pre-determined coding was used in the process as our interest was to inductively find out themes that emerged from the survey answers. The results of the two initial groupings were compared, discussed, and synthesised into one more refined thematic grouping by the workshop organisers (authors 1–7). The resulting workshop themes were given preliminary headings in order to provide a basis for group discussions arranged in the workshop (Table S1). In addition, descriptive summaries were created for the close-ended questions. These preliminary results were presented to the workshop participants.

Table S1. Workshop themes and number of pre-workshop survey answers relating to each theme.

Theme heading	Number of answers
Multidisciplinary research, governance, and politics	25
Education, science communication, and implementation	20
Human health and lifestyle	16
Ethical issues, values, and inequality	12
Economy and marketing	9
Environmental pollution, contamination, and waste	8
Anthropogenic ecosystems	5

In the workshop, a print-out of each list of theme-wise text answers was provided in the workshop to support the group discussions, although each group of participants themselves decided whether they went through the answers first or started directly discussing the given theme. The following section lists the theme-wise text answers under each theme. The answers were derived mainly in relation to the question ‘In addition to the list above, and according to your personal perception, what other aspects or study questions scientists should consider in order to achieve a more sustainable world?’. However, if the same answer and/or thought of line continued in a respondents’ answer to the question ‘Write here your other possible comments or thoughts for workshop organisers’, also that text answer was included. Note that if one answer was categorised under more than one theme, it has been copied and listed multiple times.

THEME: Multidisciplinary research, governance, and politics

- Adopt an evolutionary perspective on conservation of biodiversity and management of natural resources (e.g., consider translocations to increase adaptive potential).
- How can policymakers/stakeholders/scientists work together to understand that the targets set for developing countries need to be harmonious with social and human development goals - the pressure to lead on sustainability and environmental protection must be on the Western or developed nations. Is this a common view and is it acted upon?

- Investigating the role of citizens in modifying environmental politics
- More high-quality multidisciplinary research in high-impact journals.
- Psychologists should be more involved. How do we think and feel about climate change and other negative challenges that are facing us?
- Cultural exchange - appreciating and learning from each other. Do not assume that 'the one size shoe fits all' approach will lead to any real solution. We need to learn about each other, and from each other. Genuinely, in a mutually beneficial way. With a collective mindset we 'as humanity' will be able to tackle problems in a tailor-made, culturally appropriate way. This is where 'bottom-up' and 'top-down' need to come together, and where scientists could play a key facilitator role between policymakers and local community representatives.
- The (structural) political and power dimension of the biodiversity crisis was not enough tackled by Ripple et al. 2017 (except the 'revising our economy' component). The structures we are embedded in (various political systems, with different degrees of democracy, dictatorship, corruption, inequality; the legacy of colonisation, the economic globalisation, and the relatively recent transnational governance trend) are crucial elements that need to be considered and tackled to achieve a sustainable world.
- Cross-discipline information sharing: engage scientists from fields outside biology. Multidisciplinary work on these topics should start early, latest in the university but preferably already in primary and secondary education.
- This [Ripple et al.] is a good list of topics, but the cultural and economic mechanisms to bring about change should be further explored and acknowledged. Education and policy instruments often fall short when not combined with behavior shifts and economic incentives. E.g. we'll all drive electric cars when they are perceived as 'cool' and are as cheap as conventional cars, not when scientists try to guilt people into it. Likewise the trade in illegal wildlife products will decrease when consumers stop wanting and paying for them. Until then, of course policy instruments is useful to keep it at bay, but is not a long - term solution. We as scientists should seek mechanisms that are shown to actually change people's behaviour, like education for women and girls, and not rely too heavily on things like awareness campaigns, whose perceived political baggage often alienates and divides as much as they educate.
- In the marine realm, how are populations connected? Not only must we secure ecosystem-based management, but we also must ensure source, and not sink, populations are protected. The marine realm is a circumglobal body of water where opportunities for dispersal (and therefore for gene flow) are seemingly endless. Yet the coral reefs rival rain forests in biodiversity. So dispersal barriers do exist, but where, and why? Second, in the big picture there should not be a strict division to marine, terrestrial and aerial worlds as these are all interconnected. Coral reefs not only produce most of the oxygen we breathe, but they, together with many types of algae, are major contributors of DMS into the atmosphere. DMS in turn is the gas that contributes to the formation of clouds and scatters the solar radiation back to space - essentially affecting absolutely everything we do. We must get scientists to work together to solve how these systems work and what can we do to stop the ongoing disaster. Third, gained knowledge must be spoon-fed to those in power, so they know to make the right, evidence-based decisions - and understand the consequences of the decisions made.
- Scientists should come up with an alternative model to the monetary system. Our current system benefits a small group of people and it returns rewards for actions that do not benefit the communities or promote general well being (e.g. health and environment). Valuing the ecosystem services is taking the research to the right direction but it is not enough to make a real change. The question about sustainable human population on earth is a social one. I think there is a lot information about how earth functions but we still lack the same information about humans.
- We need more information about our environment and nature - how to measure the extinction depth or metapopulation dynamic? After that we can find out what we should do to achieve more sustainable world

- To me, conservation biology is a palliative, in the sense that it can ensure survival of ecosystems/species/habitats on the short-mid term, but it does not represent a solution to the deeper causes of global unsustainability. This is, to me, more linked to overpopulation and global socio-economic inequalities. So the main focus should be on the latter than the preservation of ecosystems/species/habitats.
- Work closely with local communities in countries where there are environmental issues to a) understand values, attitudes, resource use patterns and needs, b) ensure sustainable coexistence between nature and society, and c) provide education and outreach initiatives where appropriate.
- It is virtually impossible to pick just three priority steps as none of them stand alone. An integrated, holistic approach is needed. For this reason I had considered choosing 'increasing overall appreciation of nature' but don't believe 'appreciation' goes far enough. The mainstreaming of a fundamental understanding of the interconnectedness of global environmental systems, social systems and individual behaviours is needed to stop environmental issues being seen as outside of everyday experience and influence (particularly in industrial, increasingly urban societies). Society and nature do not exist apart from one another, and perhaps part of the problems we face today are because they have been seen as such by post-industrial populations. How do we instil a stronger, basic understanding of this into all aspects and sectors of society. That being said, and accepting that is a huge challenge, I also think there should be a far greater onus on the private sector to enable positive change. Industries of all types should be pushed to develop and adopt more environmentally responsible practices across the entire life cycle of services and products. This would remove the reliance on consumers to make 'green' purchasing decisions and so enable effective change for minimal consumer effort.
- Above all, the big questions science has to deal with are the ongoing environmental change, together with biodiversity decline and habitat loss. E.g., the recent paper by Bar-On et al. (www.pnas.org/cgi/doi/10.1073/pnas.1711842115) is an excellent reading on the matter.
- Scientists need to understand and consider economic aspects and sociological preferences, so that they can co-operate with the public and change global economic trends that affect nature. Some of these aspects are beyond understanding natural processes, because nature is competing with greater forces like economy, and only public awareness can change the balance towards preferring natural habitats over profit.
- Exploring social science methods to shift people's attitudes towards a more sustainable way of thinking and living. This can include psychology and marketing science among others.
- How can I connect my research to this bigger picture? Sometimes I see the connection clearly, sometimes I don't and sometimes I feel like I should be doing something more relevant or with bigger impact.
- Establishing sustainable land management practices so that there is less pressure on reserves to protect biodiversity
- This is a good list of topics, but the cultural and economic mechanisms to bring about change should be further explored and acknowledged. Education and policy instruments often fall short when not combined with behaviour shifts and economic incentives. E.g. we'll all drive electric cars when they are perceived as 'cool' and are as cheap as conventional cars, not when scientists try to guilt people into it. Likewise, the trade in illegal wildlife products will decrease when consumers stop wanting and paying for them. Until then, of course policy instruments is useful to keep it at bay, but is not a long - term solution. We as scientists should seek mechanisms that are shown to actually change people's behaviour, like education for women and girls, and not rely too heavily on things like awareness campaigns, whose perceived political baggage often alienates and divides as much as they educate.
- Pathways for making the aspects above [Ripple et al. list] become realised in the current political (especially international and multi-actor) reality.
- To try to have more weight in the governments' decisions.
- I think it is important to increase the diversity of people informing and participating in decision-making processes, e.g., by capacity-building in underrepresented regions. Specifically, I think that the research

community should be substantially supported in biodiversity rich countries, such as African countries, so as to diversify the scientific community, and thereby facilitate the development of innovative solutions.

- Integration of different worldviews and/or knowledge systems to tackle natural resource management. - Adopt a biocultural conservation perspective to understand the links between conservation, reducing poverty and increasing the standard of living for local people. - Promote global compromises on achieving certain sustainability goals.- Promote policies that consider long-term benefits and cost instead of just short-term ones.

THEME: Education, science communication, and implementation

- I think an often overlooked aspect of trying to generate global change for the betterment of nature is the disconnect between scientists and grassroots communities, especially rural communities and farmers. Such a disconnect is widely seen in Australia and New Zealand. In particular, I have noticed that farmers, especially dairy farmers, often feel marginalised or attacked at the very thought that they are negatively contributing to global climate change. As well as promoting a mainly plant-based diet, 'incentives' need to be put in place so that producers can alter what they produce to something more sustainable whilst not damaging their livelihood. The same can be said for promoting change from fossil fuels to sustainable energy generation. We need to engage stakeholders in these industries in a way that brings them on board with scientists. As such, I believe a major stumbling block of achieving a sustainable world is the social aspect of the conversation.
- Adaptive management of protected areas, link the gap between conservation science and conservation management. Protected areas are at the forefront of conservation efforts, and yet despite considerable progress towards the global target of having 17% of the world's land area within protected areas by 2020, biodiversity continues to decline. The field of conservation science has been hampered by the limited evidence linking management actions and measurable biodiversity outcomes (Wardon, 2017). There is an urgent need for protected areas to review from conservation targets, actions taken to outcome achieved, to trace conditions and trends in a timely manner, and together achieve the adaptive management cycle.
- I think something very important from the perspective of science in particular for a sustainable world is how information and knowledge is disseminated. Some key things that may be of particular use: - Moving towards an open source system where information is available freely to everyone across the world from all economic backgrounds. This applies to both scientific findings and also policy. - Aiming for a system of better communication where consensus, evidence and debate are properly incorporated into media, so that people can make informed decisions on environmental issues. - Generally, moving towards evidence-based policy and economy in all areas, with the goal of a sustainable human development and planet at its core.
- Pathways for making the aspects above [Ripple et al. list] become realised in the current political (especially international and multi-actor) reality.
- How can we reduce the unintended consequences of conservation interventions to ensure better sustainability of conservation initiatives? - How can we better ensure that conservation benefits reach those who are most dependant on the resources we are trying to protect, therefore helping them to change their behaviour more sustainably? - How can we ensure that conservation impact is properly measured, so that we can learn from our mistakes, ensure we aren't wasting valuable resources and improve our plans going forward?
- All 13 steps humanity can take to transition to sustainability are relevant. However, we should primarily prioritise the most achievable rather than the most important ones.
- Research needs to be translated into press releases and other relevant formats for the public. More public outreach needed.
- How do we communicate science or engage the population in science in a way which is different to our current approach, which seems to lack excitement or power to convince large amounts of people in the short term?

- I believe the way in which conservationists carry the message they want to transmit to the rest of the society should be improved and, thus get the change to a more sustainable lifestyle. I have seen that in many occasions certain groups (e.g. vegans) try to give the message to other people in a rude -and even- sectarian way. This behaviour causes the receiver to react negatively (and even violently) to the message that was wanted to transmit, rejecting it.
- Education Education Education
- As scientists we have the right tools to understand these kind of problems. We have the culture, the knowledge and the sensibility to face these issues and the possibility to work in order to solve them one day (we hope). In my opinion an important question that as scientists we should consider is: How can we explain and involve common people? Many time I notice that there is a too big division between us and the common people. However without them we can't achieve a more sustainable world.
- Third, gained knowledge must be spoon-fed to those in power, so they know to make the right, evidence-based decisions - and understand the consequences of the decisions made.
- Work closely with local communities in countries where there are environmental issues to a) understand values, attitudes, resource use patterns and needs, b) ensure sustainable coexistence between nature and society, and c) provide education and outreach initiatives where appropriate
- In light of recent development in fake news narratives and science discrediting, science communication needs improvement and to face the new challenges in social media.
- In my opinion, a key aspect is to enhance the communication of science to the public and policymakers. For this, a good first step would be to more strongly include science communication education in the doctoral programs. Social media offers wide possibilities for effective communication and should be utilised in the best possible manner.
- It's been 50 years since the climate change movement began, and 20 years since biodiversity protection came on the scene. What has worked and what hasn't - are we looking to our community to understand where we are doing the same things and expecting a different outcome? - How do we involve and promote more diverse minds and academic backgrounds into positions of power; State workers, financial directors, business men and women, politicians, and other key actors in the world's social and political scene are very seldom from a scientific background. This will and does not help get the message across. We are still seen to operate separately on an issue which is now of global and pressing concern.
- I feel like a lot of knowledge has already been created in the field of conservation science but on the other hand it seems at least to me that little of this knowledge actually is transferred to practitioners, politicians and the general public and so None of the Problems are actually solved. Sometimes I wonder if this huge amount of Money we spend to accumulate more and more detailed knowledge would not better be spent in tackling the problems directly with the knowledge Level we have already achieved. I would sometimes wish that science, especially conservation science would more often be linked to concrete Projects on the ground to generate knowledge that can directly be used by practitioners. I know of some examples where this is done and works out, but in my opinion, These are far too few.
- Integration of science in decision making.
- I believe the societal aspect of promoting global change is a huge issue. I think the workshop would benefit from discussing how best to educate society in order to get the majority on board with preventing an unsustainable future, whilst also trying to minimise affecting the most vulnerable to sustainable changes (i.e. unskilled workers, ruminant farmers, mine workers).
- We need more optimism in conservation! This [Ripple et al.] paper, while highlighting some major issues, is troubling for me. The fact that this is a second reminder shows that the first warning has been ignored, possibly because people are becoming so used to hearing the bad news that the drive to make change is dampened. Many studies in psychology and marketing have shown that people change their behaviour more readily when they believe that their actions can make a difference. Despite this, the image of conservation is increasingly

bleak, which doesn't motivate people to act. This piece from young scientists should reflect an optimistic tone, in order to show that change is possible, and that we aren't just fighting a losing battle. If we want this paper to be the first (and only) warning from young scientists, perhaps a policy brief or more digestible piece could be produced to send to policy makers and the media?

THEME: Human health and lifestyle

- I think examining the long term impacts of biodiversity loss and environmental degradation on human welfare and health is an important aspect to consider. Particularly because it is something that is likely to engage with the general population and promote a push for more sustainable policies and practices
- Connecting health to sustainability. To be able to live a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to take care of the habitat, soil, water, air, landscape, animals.. Health is a constant factor that humans have to deal with. It is an interesting question, if these values are connected with the health of the environment, do they lead to better everyday choices for a more sustainable planet?
- Encourage short distance travels and sustainable mobility.
- Lower levels of consumption (degrowth?).
- I believe the way in which conservationists carry the message they want to transmit to the rest of the society should be improved and, thus get the change to a more sustainable lifestyle. I have seen that in many occasions certain groups (e.g. vegans) try to give the message to other people in a rude -and even- sectarian way. This behaviour causes the receiver to react negatively (and even violently) to the message that was wanted to transmit, rejecting it.
- Research on how to change human behaviour to include sustainability values - change the definition of success from a material-oriented to a well-being oriented definition
- The world reacts to demand. Thus, I believe the most effective way of reducing the humankind impact on the planet is having fewer people that consume and waste less. I believe the inclusion of an 'environmental cost' to products and services would change people's perception of their value (translated into monetary cost).
- I don't support overpopulation arguments, the evidence shows it's how we live, not how many of us live that matters. Those that by far use the most resources (Western, richer nations) also have slowing populations and have done so for a while.
- Reducing consumption, particularly by targeting those with the most wealth, and changing societal norms around consumption.
- Phasing out the use of single-use plastics and petroleum products in general. -Decentralisation of energy so that each household or small community has the means of producing their own clean renewable energy with the use of solar panels, wind turbines, biomass, small hydro schemes etc. Also, financial incentives and removal of barriers for those wishing to live an off-grid, carbon neutral and more sustainable lifestyle. -Phasing out household cleaning and personal care products known to be the most detrimental to aquatic life.
- It is virtually impossible to pick just three priority steps as none of them stand alone. An integrated, holistic approach is needed. For this reason I had considered choosing 'increasing overall appreciation of nature' but don't believe 'appreciation' goes far enough. The mainstreaming of a fundamental understanding of the interconnectedness of global environmental systems, social systems and individual behaviours is needed to stop environmental issues being seen as outside of everyday experience and influence (particularly in industrial, increasingly urban societies). Society and nature do not exist apart from one another, and perhaps part of the problems we face today are because they have been seen as such by post-industrial populations. How do we instil a stronger, basic understanding of this into all aspects and sectors of society. That being said, and accepting that is a huge challenge, I also think there should be a far greater onus on the private sector to enable positive change. Industries of all types should be pushed to develop and adopt more environmentally responsible practices across the entire life cycle of services and products. This would remove the reliance on consumers to make 'green' purchasing decisions and so enable effective change for minimal consumer effort.

- Shift from meat-based agriculture to sustainable aquaculture and insect farming as less resource-intensive, intermediary solutions (relative to shifting entirely to plant-based) to reducing red meat consumption. - Further reduce the human population growth rate by promoting social systems of non-family-based community (e.g., if you know you will be taken care of in your old age, there is less reason to have children).
- Is talking about population growth a waste of time/actually damaging for conservation?
- As with diets, I believe that people's demand for goods and services could be shifted towards more sustainable choices with the right information, marketing, etc.
- Dietary shift as suggested by Ripple et al. seems to be inevitable, however, only by locally produced food on small/middle-scale organic/biodynamic farms. Food waste needs to be addressed as suggested, but, less food waste in America won't solve the hunger in Africa, and won't make the food more nutritious worldwide.
- Promoting localisation of consumption, especially food consumption. -Education and appreciation about wild foods that can be sourced from the local environment surrounding us.

THEME: Ethical issues, values, and inequality

- How can policymakers/stakeholders/scientists work together to understand that the targets set for developing countries need to be harmonious with social and human development goals - the pressure to lead on sustainability and environmental protection must be on the Western or developed nations. Is this a common view and is it acted upon?
- Rights-based approaches. First of all, tackling human-rights abuses with marginalised and indigenous communities. Secondly, giving 'rights' to non-human beings - sacred forests, animals, ecosystems...
- research on how to change human behaviour to include sustainability values - change the definition of success from a material-oriented to a well-being oriented definition
- I believe that, at the moment, two main aspects need to be studied by scientists: how unequal access to environmental resources around the world is affecting the environment and if environmental and conservation policies can help stepping towards a more equal world, by influencing also school, health, minority and women policies. The first aspect has been investigated (only in regards to biodiversity) by Holland et al. (2009).
- Fighting tax evasion and venture capitalism, which are the very basic reasons why development is not sustainable anymore. Money and capital cannot be moved across the globe, nor taxation could be eluded through tax havens. The lack of taxation is generating inequalities, undermining scientific development and funding for environmental agencies. If countries do not seriously fight these two points, biological conservation is hopeless, in the long term.
- Appropriate market instruments (taxation plus natural capital accounting) - Shift towards addressing imbalance of unequal benefits/costs of conservation (e.g. Protected Areas conflict, resource use restrictions, affect the poor most) - More effective Payments for ecosystem services, so anyone can be paid to conserve land, anywhere, seamlessly - More democratic conservation
- To me, conservation biology is a palliative, in the sense that it can ensure survival of ecosystems/species/habitats on the short-mid term, but it does not represent a solution to the deeper causes of global unsustainability. This is, to me, more linked to overpopulation and global socio-economic inequalities. So the main focus should be on the latter than the preservation of ecosystems/species/habitats.
- reducing consumption, particularly by targeting those with the most wealth, and changing societal norms around consumption.
- Reduction of inequality among developed and developing nations.
- - Can and should conservationists act to put pressure on governments and ministries to reduce corruption, where corruption is a major barrier to successful conservation? - How can we integrate local knowledge into conservation work at all levels, to ensure sustainability, suitability and desirability for local people of any interventions?

- I believe the societal aspect of promoting global change is a huge issue. I think the workshop would benefit from discussing how best to educate society in order to get the majority on board with preventing an unsustainable future, whilst also trying to minimise affecting the most vulnerable to sustainable changes (i.e. unskilled workers, ruminant farmers, mine workers).
- Should conservation try to save all the species or focus on specific species? Who and how choose the species to conserve?

THEME: Economy and marketing

- The world reacts to demand. Thus, I believe the most effective way of reducing the humankind impact on the planet is having fewer people that consume and waste less. I believe the inclusion of an 'environmental cost' to products and services would change people's perception of their value (translated into monetary cost). For instance, oil palm plantation in Southeast Asia is a profitable activity, but the 'environmental cost' is not included in the price. If it were included, the activity would no longer be attractive in financial terms, thereby halting land-use change.
- In my opinion, Ripple et al. 2017 missed a fundamental piece of the story, which has been tackled by Pacheco et al. (2018), when directly commenting on Ripple et al. paper. The main economic model is based on growth. Shifting towards green economy will not change 'growth' as the main paradigm. The risk of sustainable economy has been studied by Antal et al. (2016), showing how the shift towards green economy will not halt the current environmental crisis. I believe that, at the moment, two main aspect need to be studied by scientist: how unequal access to environmental resources around the world is affecting the environment and if environmental and conservation policies can help stepping towards a more equal world, by influencing also school, health, minority and women policies. The first aspect has been investigated (only in regards to biodiversity) by Holland et al. (2009).
- Fighting tax elusion and venture capitalism, which are the very basic reason why development is not sustainable anymore. Money and capital cannot be moved across the globe, nor taxation could be eluded through tax haven. The lack of taxation is generating inequalities, undermining scientific development and funding for environmental agencies. If countries do not seriously fight these two points, biological conservation is hopeless, in the long term.
- Appropriate market instruments (taxation plus natural capital accounting) - Shift towards addressing imbalance of unequal benefits/costs of conservation (e.g. Protect Areas conflict, resource use restrictions, affect the poor most) - New technologies, particular for improving green energy and waste - Improving the biodiversity potential of cities and restoring areas of unproductive land - More effective Payments for ecosystem services, so anyone can be paid to conserve land, anywhere, seamlessly - More democratic conservation - I don't support overpopulation arguments, the evidence shows its how we live, now how many of us live that matters. Those that by far use the most resources (Western, richer nations) also have slowing populations and have done so for a while.
- Integration of different worldviews and/or knowledge systems to tackle natural resource management. - Adopt a biocultural conservation perspective to understand the links between conservation, reducing poverty and increasing the standard of living for local people. - Re-think the way Western economy works. Lower levels of consumption (degrowth?). - Promote global compromises on achieving certain sustainability goals.- Promote policies that consider long-term benefits and cost instead of just short-term ones.
- I think an often overlooked aspect of trying to generate global change for the betterment of nature is the disconnect between scientists and grassroots communities, especially rural communities and farmers. Such a disconnect is widely seen in Australia and New Zealand. In particular, I have noticed that farmers, especially dairy farmers, often feel marginalised or attacked at the very thought that they are negatively contributing to global climate change. As well as promoting a mainly plant-based diet, 'incentives' need to be put in place so that producers can alter what they produce to something more sustainable whilst not damaging their

livelihood. The same can be said for promoting change from fossil fuels to sustainable energy generation. We need to engage stakeholders in these industries in a way that brings them on board with scientists. As such, I believe a major stumbling block of achieving a sustainable world is the social aspect of the conversation.

- Scientists should come up with an alternative model to the monetary system. Our current system benefits a small group of people and it returns rewards for actions that do not benefit the communities or promote general well being (e.g. health and environment). Valuing the ecosystem services is taking the research to the right direction but it is not enough to make a real change. The question about sustainable human population on earth is a social one. I think there is a lot information about how earth functions but we still lack the same information about humans.
- When private corporations have sometimes higher revenues than the GDP of countries the responsibility in achieving sustainable development should also focus on how private corporations can be taken accountable and assist sustainable transitions.
- Phasing out the use of pesticides by banning and/or heavily taxing them, and increase subsidies to make the more environmentally sustainable forms of pest control more affordable. Also increasing subsidies to farmers who practice organic and permaculture methods of farming.

THEME: Environmental pollution, contamination, and waste

- Contamination of the environment with chemical pollution is of increasing concern. [... *] E.g. endocrine-disrupting chemicals—particularly those that modify sex steroid signalling— and pharmaceuticals have the potential to alter animal behaviour and, in doing so, impair survival and reproductive fitness in exposed wildlife. [... *deleted some parts here that could have revealed the identity of the respondent.]
- New technologies, particular for improving green energy and waste
- In addition to the [Ripple et al.'s] list above, scientists should consider processes and policies by which we can reducing or remove environmental pollution with anthropogenic products, such as pesticides, personal care products and pharmaceuticals. Such chemicals contaminants are globally ubiquitous, and many have the propensity to impact wildlife health. Steps to reduce the impacts of these products include prioritisation for the removal dangerous substances (many of which still require toxicological testing), targeted removal of priority substances by wastewater treatment facilities, increased funding for wastewater treatment facilities and the development of products that are more easily removed by treatment process or are less harmful as environmental contaminants. [... *deleted some parts here that could have revealed the identity of the respondent.]
- Reducing other waste e.g. plastics
- Phasing out the use of pesticides by banning and/or heavily taxing them, and increase subsidies to make the more environmentally sustainable forms of pest control more affordable. Also increasing subsidies to farmers who practice organic and permaculture methods of farming. -Phasing out the use of single-use plastics and petroleum products in general. -Decentralisation of energy so that each household or small community has the means of producing their own clean renewable energy with the use of solar panels, wind turbines, biomass, small hydro schemes etc. Also financial incentives and removal of barriers for those wishing to live an off-grid, carbon neutral and more sustainable lifestyle. -Phasing out household cleaning and personal care products known to be the most detrimental to aquatic life.
- Reduction of environmental footprint and leakage effects of production systems.
- Understanding of the environmental impacts of production systems (e.g. food and energy production).
- Development of frameworks for long-term studies that allow the understanding of environmental impacts at global and regional scales.

THEME: Anthropogenic ecosystems

- Shift in disturbance regimes caused by anthropogenic factors and their effects on biodiversity and ecosystems services.
- Improving the biodiversity potential of cities and restoring areas of unproductive land
- Pastoralism supports 200 million households and is practised over 25% of the land on Earth. In the 21st century, there is the important need for a transformation of the traditional pastoralism towards sustainable pastoralism, especially in drylands to reduce pastoralism pressure toward suitable habitats for wildlife.
- Establishing sustainable land management practices so that there is less pressure on reserves to protect biodiversity
- Both conservation biologists and the society surrounding them should understand, that the line between 'nature' and 'man-made'/'altered'/'urban' is fictional: conserving species and restoring habitats should not be focused into areas far from centres of human inhabitation, but should be promoted equally in cities, urban areas and other areas heavily impacted by humans. Furthermore, neither species or habitat conservation in such modified landscapes should aim for restoring conditions that are not likely to sustain themselves but require constant input from conservationists. Rather, they should aim at gaining what benefit for biodiversity can be gained with an open mind. In practice, we should utilise what ever means (such as species or habitat conservation) are available to increase the conservation value of e.g. road verges, power line clearings, city parks, wastelands, landfills, golf courses and all other kinds of land cover types that presently have little value in conserving biodiversity but which surround a large part of the world's population in urban areas. Only thus can we reconnect people to biodiverse nature and at the same time help species and habitats continue to exist in areas which have been heavily altered by humans. In short, I guess I would say that urban conservation efforts (aiming at increasing the value of land cover types presently thought to have negligible impact in conservation) should be promoted with equal motivation and resources as the conservation of, say, rain forests, polar bears or the white-tailed eagle.

Qualitative data collection in the workshop and transcripts (workshop summaries and written notes)

The following sections provide theme-wise data collected from the workshop. The discussions were guided by the question: 'What should ECRs avoid, be careful about, and focus on while continuing their scientific careers with the aim of guiding or advancing sustainability?' Differently coloured post-it notes were available to write down the ideas (to avoid = pink, be careful about = yellow, and focus on = green). The participants could also write directly onto a large sheet of paper that covered the table, which also allowed for the last group to move the post-it notes around and draw connections between the notes on that table. After the workshop each table was photographed and the notes on them were collected and anonymised for further analysis by groups of authors, and archival by author 1. Note that the photographs are not included in this Supporting Information as they show handwriting, which would allow for identification of the participants. The group summaries presented at the end of the workshop were transcribed verbatim, and written notes left to each discussion table were grouped according to the type of each note.

Theme: Multidisciplinary research, governance, and politics

Summary transcript

"So, we discussed and we reorganised all what we saw in the tables plus our discussion. I think we identified four main themes that have emerged across the things: the papers and the discussion."

"The first [subtheme: GET INVOLVED POLITICALLY], let's say... a call to get involved politically, and the questioning of the current system, and people calling for being more radical... stop being politically neutral. Basically, get involved

politically. Some people wanting to say that there is not one political solution but several. Some saying, we need more political discussion within conservation and not being afraid of conflict. We need to challenge the continuous growth model and everything. And the thing of not always staying with like-minded people, but to basically go and talk to others.”

“The second theme [TACKLE THE FUNDING POLITICS], it’s more that as a group we discussed that, we ended up discussing the funding politics. And to say, we discussed a bit what happened, and what was discussed this morning, in the plenary session, and to say how can we actually get involved in the society, communicate our science, talk to or get involved with decision-makers and everything, when we are always running out of funding. Or having to publish and all this kind of things. So there is now more demand to get good results when there is no money, there... is like someone was saying, we need a revolution of science. To get involved and potentially politically, having to incline [to say to] society that we can’t do a good job if we don’t have job security, basically. There is too much time that goes into applying money, there is not enough time for doing meaningful science which is inefficient, yeah, we need job security. That’s a big dimension; if we want to make something meaningful, then we need to be able to structurally to do so.”

“Then there was a big debate, so people don’t agree with [each other], there are different colours, green and yellow and... pink. [THEME 3: INTER-, MULTI-, AND TRANSDISCIPLINARITY] About interdisciplinarity and multidisciplinary. [...] So, people saying, try to be more involved in, don’t get too detrimental to other disciplines, some people wanting that multidisciplinary should not be the goal, it should be a tool. Be aware of fake multidisciplinary.”

“Like some people say, we need to be careful about focusing too much on multidisciplinary approach because we still need experiments on specific topics. [...] Some calling for, you should have your PhD in different disciplines, mixing things, some others more like be careful of at it, it can have perverse effects.”

“And the last theme was about getting involved with the public, or the societies [GET INVOLVED WITHIN SOCIETY]. So it was more diverse. Some people saying, we should speak the same language with the stakeholders; some others that don’t always trust stakeholders, people are stupid and selfish... [laughter on the background]”

“Sorry I forgot something... Someone saying about, before, about multi- or interdisciplinarity, saying that there is some old-fashioned fields that should be valued, that maybe it is good sometimes to just be in some old-fashioned field, and not doing this fancy interdisciplinarity.”

“So, people saying, bring conservation into politic[al] rooms. Go and tell the science side of the story, even if we are not sure yet. And not go after outside fashions. And some people say, if you go on to get involved with the society that’s good, but be careful, for example there was a discussion about youth education that is important, if you want to make a change, then you should go and educate youth. But beware – we were having a discussion, because... you should be careful about... like, with brainwashing.”

“And then, someone saying you don’t have to get out of the ivory tower, if this means weakening your science. So a lot going on, basically, in how to engage with the public, citizens, there is also the role, don’t forget the role of citizens. And we cannot afford the discussion on how this should be done, and what should be the reward into that.”

Written notes

Avoid:

- Don’t get stuck inside the system!
- There is not one political solution (system) but several ones that need to be adapted to regional context

- Don't always trust 'stakeholders', people are stupid and selfish

Be careful about:

- Youth education important but careful with brainwashing
- You don't have to get out of the 'ivory tower' if this mean weakening your science
- There may be value in old-fashioned 'fields' too that should not be ignored?
- Be careful not to take multidisciplinary as the goal. It is a tool
- Be aware of fake multidisciplinary
- Be careful about focussing too much on multidisciplinary approach because we still need experts on specific topics

Focus on:

- Tell the science side of the story (even if we're not sure yet), and don't go after "outside fashions"
- Try to be involving don't be too judgemental
- Challenging the funding politics
- Bring conservation issues in politic rooms (parliaments)
- Municipality level work
- The role of citizens to create political change at different levels.
- Speak the same language as stakeholders
- Do address the science-policy gap / research-implementation gap.
- Interdisciplinary approach should start at early stage (primary & secondary schools)
- Aim to have at least 1 part of your PhD from another field than the others (e.g. biology vs. sociology)
- Economy, marketing, "fashion" psychology, tourism, politics/policy, planning
- It is rarely black and white. So be aware that there are always more sides of the medal.
- Don't only look/speak/read opinions/science of like-minded people, but go out and speak to opponents or non-informed persons. Form your own opinion
- Forget conventions and be radical! Status quo ≠ politically neutral
- Be more radical!
- Vote & Look out for / promote democracy
- Need more political discussions within conservation
- Not being afraid of conflict and challenge the system and continuous growth

Theme: Education, science communication, and implementation

Summary transcript

"You need to communicate your results. It can be you or then someone else. So if you do not want to do it yourself, get help from science communicators. You should get the science out since you need to get heard. That was theme one."

"When communicating, be aware of scientific language. Make your message clear but do not be too modest. It also must be true of course so you need to find the balance. Scientific language has to be in such away so that you can mainstream it and public can understand your results easily. Avoid jargon and try to make it simple. You can practice it by talking to normal people that this is what I'm doing, for example."

"Then there was a big green blob, it's about natural education especially for very young people, like in elementary school. It should be normal to get nature education or when you do it on your spare time it should normal and not to feel being a weird guy going out watching the birds. We really have to think how we can mainstream doing things in nature. Like nature conservation but also nature study and when you are young then maybe on elementary school like adults telling that this tree is way old and super cool and then you are like, aa that's cool let me climb it. And when

you are older and in puberty then one thing you don't want to is get told by an adult you have to do this and it's nice and blablabla. So then you need to have peers who do it and then you have to have social component and then you and mainstreaming it by nature education we think."

"Policy makers. Work together with them. Involve stakeholders throughout the research process. Like this morning in IPBES presentation, from a start on involve policy makers but be aware of the power relationships between stakeholders when involving them in research like politicians can be saying only things that are only beneficial for their own agenda or objects of interest. And have a communication plan basically."

"The last topic is conflicting but there is more agreement than it looks. Look at the big picture, be careful not to being too narrow minded and living in a bubble. Don't ignore social science. Talk to people."

"The last thing is a reality check, so do not be too pessimistic or too optimistic: so be realistic."

Written notes

Avoid:

- Scientific jargon when talking to non-scientific people
- Do not be too modest
- Don't ignore social science or live in a bubble
- Being too narrow-minded

Be careful about:

- When involving politicians, be careful with their own agendas/objectives/interests
- Power relationships between stakeholders when involving them in research
- Living in a bubble
- Do not be too pessimistic/optimistic
- Get the science out with science communication. Do it yourself or with help from science communicators

Focus on:

- Clear messages
- Expand the education to ethics, economy and politics
- Get help from science communicator
- More media training, co-operation
- Actively communicate with your university media team/offices
- Scientific language to mainstreaming language to make the public more
- Get kids into the nature and let them be inspired
- Nature/environmental education
- Later, use peer to peer education. Make it socially acceptable /cool to go into nature
- Try to connect nature with everyday life
- Teach environmental courses on basic ecology/sustainability
- Show the world that young conservationists are actually quite normal people
- Work with policy makers
- Involve stakeholders through the research process
- Have a communication plan agreed with a large community of scientists
- Big picture

Theme: Human health and lifestyle

Summary transcript

"Our theme is called human health and lifestyle. We identified three different themes where we have a bunch of different recommendations and with some general attitude recommendations to keep in mind. The first one is

everyday life which is a mix a lot of a bike, people want more bikes, or more bike lanes probably, and bike more, they can go hand in hand so, we need to go more by wheels and we need more help from society to have more bike lanes. We have to be aware of the number of children we get, it might affect your health and maybe more to the climate and environment. And free access to family planning is needed. We have one point here which we also be aware is pets, because they might have a quite big impact on environment. Maybe you are vegan or vegetarian but your pets eat a lot of meat for instance. Then we have some... So our next category was travel. So we talked about discouraging frequent travel overseas both for personal holidays but also for meetings, so encouraging online participation for example or for larger events like this, focusing on the sustainability of them. And then also on a kind of on a more personal travel side, the engagement of humans with more local nature so we have ecotourism on a yellow post-it and, but with a green post-it connecting. Focusing on, you know, enjoying on what you have on your doorstep and not losing in sight of that if you want to be an ecotourist you can do that on your own neighborhood. And I will finish with consumption, so we identified people who want to eat more local foods and there was also something about good to be a vegetarian or vegan, like sort of avoiding the use of animal based products but we also saw yellow cards like for being careful of, healthy foods can also have impacts, footprints on... yeah. After on have to shift from like luxury items to other things... sort of big things like plastic [bottled] water... like water is, everything is plastic... Discourage alcohol use, cigarette use, sugar, which is interesting, haha. To conclude, the attitudes: so it's good to consider all aspects locally and culturally as well. Relax, do not stress so much about saving the world. And I'll finish like: think global, act local."

Written notes

Avoid:

- Frequent travel overseas
- Alcohol use, cigarette use, sugar
- Plastics, for example disposable plastic bottles
- Animal based products

Be careful about:

- Pets – consider predation of local wildlife, meat and other resources
- Number of children
- Sustainable ecotourism, that could generate income for developing areas
- Relax. Do not stress too much about saving the world
- Consider all aspects locally and culturally
- Use taxation to encourage a dietary shift towards being more sustainable (and healthy)
- Healthy food can have huge environmental footprint

Focus on:

- Recycling, e.g. compost
- More bike lanes
- Cycle, cycle, cycle. Do not drive to work, but walk/cycle when travelling within city. Good for environment & health
- Better public transport, optimal = free
- Sex education
- Free access to family planning
- Encourage online meetings instead of long distance travel – when possible
- Make events sustainable (Conferences, Festivals)
- Engagement of humans to nature e.g. through activity, ecotourism
- Enjoy your local nature
- Think global, Act local

- Vegetarian lifestyle
- Shift priority from luxury items (e.g. cigarettes, alcohol) to necessities (e.g. farm based food production) or commodities
- Sign up as vegan at conferences & other events (to encourage organisers to think about the matter)
- Less consumption
- Buy local products
- Consume locally produced food

Theme: Ethical issues, values, and inequality

Summary transcript

“So the third group was on ethical issues, values and equality. We basically grouped into four themes that have been added up over the past round so that the first one is very personal: someone said, donate for good causes up to 10% of your annual income, and then live a life by example, and that kind of goes into the next theme, someone said mindfulness in research and everyday life, researches should bring these ethical issues also into your daily research life so that includes sharing co-authorship with people, give them due credit, incorporate the human dimension into conservation research, and also empowering scientists from so-called developing regions, and collaborate with animal rights causes, so that’s what you can do in your everyday research. Then we had a big theme on including local and indigenous communities into decision making, see this as an asset to your research, and then general don’t impose your Western views and values, don’t be patronising, yeah, these kinds of issues. And then the fourth one is on economy and taxes, so global collaboration in tax system and then, yeah, against venture capitalism, corruption, all that kind of things, and oh yeah that sustainability may be a source of inequality so only some people can afford to be sustainable and others cannot, so that was the economic dimension of that.”

Written notes

Avoid:

- Impose western values and views in research
- Pund speaking
- Corruption

Be careful about:

- Sensitive discussions on ‘Indigenous’ or ‘local’ people
- Ethical issues with your own colleagues
- Sustainability may hide source of inequality within the current economic system
- venture capitalism

Focus on:

- Empower scientists and practitioners from developing countries
- Involve local communities and indigenous people in conservation management
- Collaborate with multiple stakeholders and subjects (social scientists, anthropologists, animal rights followers, etc.)
- Incorporate human dimension (marginal communities, indigenous people and their knowledge) in conservation research
- Green development
- Global collaboration in tax systems

Theme: Economy and marketing

Summary transcript

“We are in the table of economy and marketing. We saw in the end that every topic goes more or less to topics of economic system. Marketing was mentioned couple of times but not so much.

“First we have some points of the problem we have. Maybe well-being is depending on the country and its context. We can't really impose our view of economy on the other countries. Like we can't tell to so-called developing countries to have less economic development than we had in the past.

“Then there is a short comment of to being aware of ecosystem services framework because it can also be problematic: how it works in our system and it can also cause biodiversity depletion so I would say that this is an anthropogenic view of the ecosystem that we always need to put a price tag on things.

“Then someone switched to the topic of consumption. It is also connected to the economy and we have some points of what could the possible solutions be and are they also problematic? There's for example the point of if we can include the environmental cost into the economic cost of the product which is also problematic because if price increases there will be a lot of people who can't afford it anymore. And then there is the point of green growth. Is it actually a solution to our system or is it just green washing of normal economic growth. It is closely correlated to bioeconomy, so if we turn to bioeconomy, where do all the resources come from. And can we do a fossil fuel phase out or is there trade-offs of moving to more sustainable energy systems.

“Our conclusion in the end was that we cannot live in a more sustainable world in this current economic system and that basically we do need to disconnect from the idea of capitalism and disconnect from the idea of growth as one of the main achievements in our lives. And also avoid the solutions that work within the system as they are not long-term and sustainable.

“So system change and... Yeah, it's quite broad and difficult to do in an individual level. One idea was not to support the companies anymore that profit from the capitalist system, for example to switch to social entrepreneurship and in your own life to switch to the more fair or more sustainable option. And support an anti-capitalism development for example through demonstrating.”

Written notes

Avoid:

- Avoid solutions that work within the system. They might not work in the long-term

Be careful about:

- Bioeconomy! - Where do all the resources come from? - Trade-offs in moving toward more sustainable energy system.
- More sustainable world will not happen under the current economic system.
- Being aggressive toward corporations
- Include full economic costs of environment into price without damaging poorer populations

Focus on:

- Research topic: Is it possible for all humans to access to 'European level of wellbeing' without damaging and depleting ecosystems?
- How can developing countries exploit their resources to get to the same level of development as rich countries, without degrading environment?
- The new system approach/model needs to be context dependent! - Countries in different state development.

- System change.
- Disconnect from the idea of growth.
- Disconnect from the idea of growth capitalism.
- Don't support the system.
- Green growth = green washing?
- Don't support companies that profit from capitalist system - switch to social entrepreneurship
- We as researchers need to show the connection between human wellbeing and biodiversity conservation.
- Study negative environmental externalities and integrate them in the economy with financial instruments
- More wellbeing.
- New research which takes biodiversity into account.

Theme: Environmental pollution, contamination, and waste

Summary transcript

“How to invoke people to reducing consumption which can in turn affect production, and reduction in production:

- 1) scientists providing better knowledge about the alternatives like green technologies
- 2) be more deliberate in monitoring our own waste production
- 3) ways to improve public awareness; there were seven different notes from different aspects; from global impacts and things like spill-over effect to plastic etc.

There is a big demand on buy less, promote people to buy less.

We need more knowledge that is targeted to policymakers and better technologies:

- 1) examine questions like which policies are better; stick or carrot, more subsidies or penalties on producers
- 2) there is a big gap in this section of more studies for better policy actions

More studies of the trade-offs because some of the new technologies, like wind, solar and nuclear have effects on other aspects of biodiversity or on ecosystem services and peoples' well-being, so these tradeoff should be studied before we can give further recommendations.”

Written notes

Avoid:

- Don't buy so much and so poor quality
- Consumption effect spill over -> taxes for ... Europe
- Government should not exclusively drive research.
- Current policy does not work!

Be careful about:

- Trade-offs
- More research on environmental impacts of clean technology

Focus on:

- Active inclusion of novel pollution into research (e.g. less known contaminants)
- More studies about pollution policy tools (penalties vs. subsidies)
- Monitor your own waste production more
- Promote green engineering (e.g. in chemistry)
- Change policy; solar and water energy belongs to people, not electricity companies
- Better environmental awareness is needed
 - More campaigns
 - More information about the less-known contaminants
- Use more sustainable products and less plastic
- Consumption spill over effect -> Awareness!

- Media coverage where possible

Theme: Anthropogenic ecosystems

Summary transcript

“So... our topic was anthropogenic ecosystems... which, at first we realised was a bit of a... there was some discussion about what that meant... direct..directly anthropogenic ecosystems. We classified this for example an urban, agricultural/aquacultural and hunting and fishing. But there are also most or if not all, we decided, ecosystems, were anthropogenic...ly affected, for example indirectly for pollution and climate change... so whether there is non-anthropogenic ecosystems at this point... is... unclear. So we focused, we decided to focus on the directly anthropogenic ecosystems. And then we kind of went through the variety of ideas for independent... actions as well as more broadly, yeah policied, type actions. And this was all considered under the scope of values. So I will just go through each ecosystem quickly.

“So, urban we have some examples: Consider in the area you choose to live, the level the ecological impacts it generates... consider your energy power sources, monitoring and supporting an urban wildlife, support and encourage the green architecture and green urban planning, and city planning of course. Prioritise pedestrian, cyclists, public transport. And finally private cars... so NOT prioritise those at all I guess.

“...Planting of no native species also came in the, play, something to consider in this context, and that all takes us in to agricultural as well, because that goes for both urban and agricultural systems... But some more... support community agriculture and also urban agriculture and gardening came up, some more local ideas... an individual sustainability. So individual gardening, vegetable gardens for example. Avoid products that promote land reduce change... [for] example palm oil. Then we have environmentally friendly food shopping... improving systems for labeling sustainable products... so you can tell the different types agricultural or aquacultural systems and hunting and fishing practices to better, make individual choices about eating sustainably.

“And finally in hunting and fishing category we only had: just considering the role of humans as apex predators in ecosystems... So more considering humans are just one of many predators and animals and thinking more in an ecosystem way instead of humans separate from the ecosystem. And these are all areas for research of course, and these are all considered under the values’ systems, where to focus. There was a debate apparently in previous sessions about whether to consider nature and humans together or to consider all complete separation of humans and nature... Which was considered, we decided to be impossible, but promoting positive impression, at changing the attitudes to cultural values and emotions, all of this needs to be considered in these choices and focusing only on conserving natural nature is also something to consider in that. I think that’s pretty much what we had.”

Written notes

Avoid:

- Avoid products that promote land use change, e.g. palm oil (deforestation)
- Human-mediated dispersal (unintentional) of species / populations, through personal and customer choices.

Be careful about:

- Consider your energy (power) sources
- Planting of non-native species
- Consider role of humans as apex predators in ecosystems
- Focus on conserving only natural nature
- Cultural values / emotions driving conservation

Focus on:

- Human + nature coexistence
- Promoting positive impression + changing attitudes towards
- OR: complete separation of humans and nature!
- Consider the area in which you choose to live, the level of ecological impacts it generates.
- Monitoring and/or promotion of urban wildlife
- Support / encourage green architecture & green urban planning
- In city planning: pedestrians =1, cyclists = 2, public transport = 3, private cars = 4.
- Support community agriculture
- Promote and inform on sustainable gardening and planting practices (e.g. what pesticides to avoid...)
- Promote individual sustainability, e.g. vegetable gardens
- Environmentally aware food shopping (e.g. palm oil causes land degradation)
- Improve systems for labelling sustainable products.

Qualitative analysis and analytical memos

After the workshop, the organisers (authors 1-7) contacted those participants who had expressed interest in the analysis of the collected data and writing of the current paper (authors 8-30). As the full author team was formed, we again divided ourselves into smaller groups according to the workshop themes. Each of these author groups took responsibility for analysing data collected under one of the workshop themes. There was one workshop organiser in each group facilitating the collaboration and making sure that everyone had access to the anonymised data and any relevant information underlying the project.

The groups received shared guidelines for the analysis, which followed an inductive content analysis process described by Holliday (2007) and Elo and Kyngäs (2008). The analysis was guided by the question: ‘How can we move towards a more sustainable world?’ with a specification that ‘the [resulting] manuscript will not be built around a list of what we young scientists (or humanity in general, as in the Ripple et al. paper) should do to save the planet. Rather, it will be built around a reflection on what and how we think about ways of saving the planet, or “what is the future of conservation science”’.

The content analysis, done in groups, included the following steps:

1. Going through the written notes collected from the thematic workshop table, summarising the content and writing down initial ideas.
2. Reading the transcript of the conclusive discussion summary, and collaboratively writing an analytical interpretation based on that and the written notes.
3. Reading the text answers from the pre-workshop survey under the given theme and finding out if there was something that added new information to the aspects that emerged from the workshop materials.

Steps 1-3 resulted in rather long text files that were essentially collections of different ideas pouring from the analysed data. A common factor was that the material included suggestions on three levels (global, discipline, and individual). In order to sharpen the interpretation and to develop more coherent arguments, the groups were asked to develop more concise analytical memos for the results of the content analysis, using the three-level categorisation:

4. Based on the previous analytical work, collaboratively write a new concise document where you answer the following questions: 1) What new global perspectives that Ripple et al. (2017) do not acknowledge, emerge from this research?, 2) What topics conservation science should study, and how these topics should/could be researched? 3) What is the role of researchers in the future?

The resulting analytical memos are presented in the following sections.

Theme: Multidisciplinary research, governance, and politics

The young scientists expressed a strong will to save the Earth. Yet, conservation scientists alone cannot achieve global sustainability; they need to collaborate with other scientists and other people (with different values, backgrounds, societal positions, and from different cultures) and embrace the diversity of both the ecosystems and the human systems. This leads to the importance of true multidisciplinary research. Conservation science needs to venture into multidisciplinary and participatory research while retaining a deep understanding on the ecosystems' structures, functionalities, and interconnectedness. Traditional fields of science are important, as they provide deeper understanding. At the same time, implementation of this knowledge through conservation action is inherently multidisciplinary; thus diversity in scientific method is a virtue. Multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinarity are means to an end. This so-called 'good multidisciplinary' should be based on a consensus on where multidisciplinary work and research has been successful in promoting conservation efforts. For example, there should be more emphasis on psychology and sociology, as we lack knowledge on how social systems and human minds work. Understanding and influencing the values, emotions, thoughts, and actions of humans is one of the key tools for sustainability and coexistence with nature. Political engagement requires understanding of people's opinions, as well as socio-economic status in order to appeal to a large cross-section of society.

There is a need for conservation scientists to get involved and participate socially and politically, in exemplary and innovative ways. This call for bigger societal and political role for scientists replaces the old thinking of neutrality and objectiveness as fundamental basis for being a credible scientist. Stepping out from the classical independent role of scientists is demanding for individual researchers, but through collaboration it is possible for them to achieve both high-quality science and larger influence over society. Collaboration and participation require scientists to be open to different opinions and to base their stand on facts and intellectual, critical interpretation of their own and others' voices. The goal of producing new knowledge that can inform solving of environmental issues should be kept clear and aimed at through solid research. In addition, scientists need to reach out to the public and promote the implementation of scientific knowledge. Science outreach, networking, and mainstreaming, becomes possible by being active inside and outside of the world of science. This means engaging in research-related public discussions, challenging paradigmatic thinking, and being radical – also on political arenas.

Important ethical questions arise while doing science and implementing its results, and scientists need to protect the integrity of research. Stronger connections between science, policy, and practice need to be built for effective implementation of scientific findings. Answering this need is essentially a delicate process of searching and finding the common grounds among stakeholders, with bringing their different points of view together. Therefore, albeit researchers need to engage more into political discussion and decision-making, the way this is done should be ethically reasoned and critically evaluated.

Finally, the young scientists are concerned on the scarcity of resources for doing meaningful, high-quality science. Due to frequent and pervasive competition for resources, researchers spent more time on funding applications and less time on actual research. The current situation also causes more exploitation of young scientists who are poorly paid or who sometimes work for free.

Theme: Education, science communication, and implementation

1) What new global perspectives that Ripple et al. (2017) do not acknowledge, emerge from this research?

Science communication, implementation and education. However, these topics are very general and not novel but more like how science should be done and how it should interact with societies. Moreover, education of women was mentioned in Ripple. Nevertheless, more education is needed for different groups of people on all levels. In today's world, there is infinite amount of knowledge so being able to evaluate the reliability of the news source is vital.

2) What topics conservation science should study, and how these topics should/could be researched?

Any specific study topics did not emerge from the theme 2. In general, the gap between science and policy/decision making should be reduced. Applied and interdisciplinary research are not novel things but they are needed more. Stakeholders and policy makers should be involved in scientific projects throughout the processes but this has to be transparent. Social media provides new possibilities but also challenges. Open science should be increased so that all people have an access to results.

3) What is the role of researchers in the future?

Our generation of young scientists needs to be more radical. Scientists have to communicate with the society. Science communication for public is needed more and it has to be clear. Messages are often negative so also positive success stories should be told. PhD students should have more training on science communication and universities/research groups should have science communicators.

Theme: Human health and lifestyle

1) What new global perspectives that Ripple et al. (2017) do not acknowledge, emerge from this research?

As for Ripple et al., there is no mention of the inherent value issue at all - and no discussion of the impacts of environmental illness (to use a metaphor) on human health apart from warning of doom for the biosphere and, thereby implied, ourselves. To sum up: by actively increasing communication about environment-health connections, we could passively increase environmental values and decrease consumption. This will also reduce health inequality, because a healthy environment benefits everyone (but perhaps the economic group has something to add about the impacts of wealth on health inequality).

Dietary changes: Ripple et al. also mention dietary changes as priority (plant-based foods), however I feel that the main difference in our discussion was a strong focus on local products. This aspect was never mentioned in Ripple et al. but seems to be important for some of us.

Education (and number of children): There was a focus on reducing population growth and family planning as in Ripple et al.; however, there was also some indication that for a few of us the way humans live is equally or more important than the number of humans in the planet (there seems to be a call for balance here, the number is not everything). – On the other hand, it was mentioned that we ourselves should be aware on the number of children we get.

Societal values: Here is potentially one of the main important differences compared to Ripple et al. In our discussion (and survey) we mentioned a few times the importance of changing the current overall society values (economical growth) to other values such as human health and welfare integrated with ecosystems/nature health. Ripple et al. do not directly mention change of values in their key steps for sustainability. Again, in our discussion was mentioned the importance of considering all these aspects locally and culturally.

2) What topics conservation science should study, and how these topics should/could be researched?

One idea could be to include more explicit connections between our conservation work and human/societal health in our papers and presentations. We all know they're there, but our audience doesn't necessarily think about them.

Research connecting human health and biodiversity loss / environmental degradation; Research on how to change human behaviour (there's a connection here with the increasing importance of social sciences in conservation); Increase communication between the scientific sphere and the society.

3) What is the role of researchers in the future?

No comments on this, but all the above points can be considered by us as individuals (private life of researchers).

Theme: Ethical issues, values, and inequality

1) What new global perspectives that Ripple et al. (2017) do not acknowledge emerge from this research?

The writing of Ripple et al. reflects a survivalist discourse, where the focus is on a need to mitigate human impacts on the environment by way of controlling human populations and human resource use. As compared with Ripple et al., the young scientists tended to represent a discourse based on the concept of sustainable development, where reduced inequality among humans and economic development are seen as key to furthering conservation efforts. In particular, global inequality was emphasised by the young scientists as a crucial issue intertwined with conservation: for example, developed nations should bear the brunt of conservation efforts, and conservation should not hinder improvements in economic development and social justice in developing countries. Some of the discussions by the young scientists took the highly integrated view of conservation, economic development, and social justice even further, linking biodiversity loss to the currently prevailing economic and political ideologies and their tendency to generate unhealthy materialism, corruption, and human rights abuses. What is then needed to mitigate the biodiversity crisis is deeper cultural change in terms of political systems, societal norms, and the human-nature relationship.

In addition to steps to control human population and behaviour, the actions called for by Ripple et al. include several ways to control non-human nature, for example, by the establishment and management of reserves, restoration, and rewilding. Conversely, the young researchers mainly focused on governance and control of other humans and the ethical issues relevant to that. There was no mention of conservation as a form of governance over non-human nature with its own ethical and political dimensions.

2) What topics conservation science should study, and how these topics should/could be researched?

Conservation science should study the connections among biodiversity loss, economic development, equality between humans, and social justice, for example, to harmonise conservation goals with social development goals and to reveal the causal links between political misconduct and conservation failures.

3) What is the role of researchers in the future?

The young scientists tend to view scientists as experts whose right to manage and control others (both other people and nature) is legitimate, and as key actors who should be in central governing positions. Even though the value of local and traditional knowledge and the importance of empowering local communities, indigenous peoples, and marginalised groups was highlighted, scientists were presented as the ones who (should) hold the power to consider and legitimise the inputs of other people. While broad social phenomena and prevailing societal norms were widely challenged or disapproved by the young scientists, their own values were legitimised and portrayed as an aspiration for others: the society at large should be educated to follow what scientists say. This was despite the fact that the

young scientists themselves demonstrated a diversity of worldviews and ethical positions, as suggested, for example, by the varying degrees of radicalism reflected in their responses. This diversity was, however, not explicitly acknowledged and value-conflicts within conservation were thus not discussed.

Theme: Economy and marketing

1) What new global perspectives that Ripple et al. (2017) do not acknowledge, emerge from this research?

Three major issues (a–c):

a) Defining the concept of well-being. Maybe it would be interesting to start by defining what is the concept of well-being. Because if well-being is currently defined by 'the living standards of Western countries', then it sets the 'goal' for all those 'non-Western countries'. Which will mean that, for achieving well-being they will have to have similar patterns of consumption as we have now. Which we all know that it is not sustainable. So maybe it would be necessary to start by re-thinking what well-being means, and what is the 'future' that we are heading to. Which is linked also with the idea of 'modernity'. How do we break/change these current ideas? In economic terms, defining the concept of well-being would mean defining e.g. the level of consumption necessary to make people 'well'. This, again, would define e.g. the limits to sustainable human population size (which is the final step in Ripple et al. 2017). These would allow numerical goals set for nations, which are always easier to understand and aspire than verbal goals.

Concerning the above-mentioned: If satisfactory consumption leading to wellbeing was defined e.g. according to an ecological footprint of an average American, we would need five earths to live sustainably. It is easy to calculate, this means either decreasing human population from the current 7.6 billion to 1.5 billion or setting the maximum ecological footprint globally on the level of 80% lower than that of an average American.

b) Ethical issues concerning the right to consume. A comment in the workshop sheet asked: Do developing countries have the right to consume and to exploit their natural resources? The question should not be framed this way, but rather consider if 'Western countries', such as European countries, USA etc. have the right to exploit natural resources of other countries. It could be introduced through the concept of 'resource curse phenomenon': the tendency of resource rich (and mineral rich, in particular) economies to underperform in economic growth and other development outcomes. For example, it could be explained the case of Coltan in Democratic Republic of Congo, which is used in advanced technology products, which are not consumed in DRC, but cause the prolonging of war crimes and human rights abuses. And the same with a lot of other products such as gold, cacao, coffee...

Similarly as in previous paragraph, do developing countries have an ethical right to consume? Maybe this whole issue should be turned upside down: instead of western people (who have most of the power in the world) asking whether developing countries have the ethical right to do things westerns are doing, we should ask more often that do westerns have the right? If the reality is such (as it seems to be) that human population will not decrease in a sustainable level (given western living standards), westerns should start to decrease their own demands of living standards to a sustainable level (given the human population size). Here it links again with the idea of re-defining what is well-being and the need to de-growth.

c) Change of the economic system. The main economic model is based on growth. Shifting towards green economy will not change 'growth' as the main paradigm. The risk of sustainable economy has been studied, showing how the shift towards green economy will not halt the current environmental crisis. Linked to the comments against green-growth and growth in general. Growth is perceived as evil and not necessary in real life. Therefore, new direction can only be found outside the system; in the inside, 'growth' is a dogma.

Many young researchers seem to perceive that the change of the system is inevitable, whatever is/are the new system(s) and however the change will happen. They seem not to believe in the ability of the current pervasive economic ideology and system to be able to repair environmental problems. Instead, they seem to think the solution is outside. How to do such a systemic change: Market regulation got support: setting limits to consumption and ending unregulated markets were suggested. Solutions working within the current system were asked to avoid, as they might not work in the long-term. Switching to the social entrepreneurship (concerning SE, see also question 'What topics conservation science should study...') and the concept of de-growth were suggested. Changes in demand and supply were called for, as also reducing the power of marketing. One comment asked not to support companies profiting from capitalist system. Several comments focused on criticising methods already developed to aspire more sustainable consumption: Green growth was questioned to be green washing and bio-economy was asked to be an issue that should be regarded with carefulness as all the resources come in any case from ecosystems. Aggressive approaches did not receive acceptance, although some published research papers support that.

2) What topics conservation science should study, and how these topics should/could be researched?

There were a suggestion to study negative environmental externalities and their integration into the economy with financial instruments, whereas another comment warned that inclusion of full economic environmental costs into prices needs to be done in a way that poorer populations will not be damaged. Additionally, studying incentives and regulation, and their effects to environmental externalities was asked to not only study and publish, but also lobby the results to decision makers.

A comment in the pre-survey suggested that the inclusion of environmental costs could change people's perception of their value. However, it is possible that in order to make people 'value' the costs of their consumption choices it, including environmental costs would not eliminate the environmental 'impact', but just turn it into a monetary value and – possible – make that product accessible only to a rich elite. And including full environmental externalities still means that we are accepting them, while a change can only happen with a drastic shift. For instance, high prices for plastic shoppers did not solve any problem, but a full ban can.

In the pre-workshop survey there are some other ideas, which would probably fall in the category of 'solutions within our current system': fighting tax elusion, new technologies for improving energy and waste, payments for ecosystem services, democratic conservation, increasing subsidies... But if we include these ideas, it would be necessary to have a critical approach on why they have worked or not, and what are their limits.

Why the consumer choice needs to depend exclusively on the price? What about the role of education to change the patten of consumption? A more informed / educated / conscious consumer would choose not only based on the price, but also on some other criteria: what is the origin or that product? What are the environmental and social consequences of consuming that product? Sustainability is not only about the 'ecological impact', but also at the overall picture.

When thinking about the direction of research, there were a few comments on the pre-survey that have not been included here, although they may be kind of general for the different themes: bridging the gap between scientists and grassroots communities, consider biocultural approaches, integration of different worldviews and knowledge systems...

What do we consider as 'social entrepreneurship' (SE)? Would be interesting to define it. It seems there can be define two types of SE: compensatory and transformative. Despite both aim to have a social impact, SE compensatory is still a market-based solution, while SE transformative seeks to change the global capitalism system (based on literature). We would need to define clearly, which one we are referring to if that is our 'solution' for the new direction.

3) What is the role of researchers in the future?

No comments on this!

Theme: Environmental pollution, contamination, and waste

1) What new global perspectives that Ripple et al. (2017) do not acknowledge, emerge from this research?

In Ripple et al. human-induced pollution was not a primary focus. Human-induced pollution is a powerful force shaping ecosystems and effecting conservation efforts. The tools suggested for mitigating the impacts of human-induced pollution on ecosystems are similar to those indicated for addressing problems outlined in other themes of this article. Such tools include industry level taxation and subsidies, as well as personal choices which reflect the best environmental practices (i.e. leading by example, avoiding certain products with know ecological impacts).

2) What topics conservation science should study, and how these topics should/could be researched?

Research should not be driven by society, but instead, should be driven by scientific experts of each specific field of research. For example, public concern will often focus on the most 'visible' forms of pollution (e.g. plastics, large-scale oil spills, mining contamination), and although these types of pollution are essential to address, less visible and emergic forms of pollution require a larger proportion of research focus. With a focus on emerging contaminants, conservation efforts can become less reactionary and more preventive.

3) What is the role of researchers in the future?

We need to effectively communicate this research to the broader community if we want to shift public attention to emerging contaminants as well as shape public opinion on best 'green' practices. BUT Science communication won't be enough to solve this major issue. Aiming to change public behaviour by increasing public awareness on a problem is unlikely to suffice, because people base their behaviour on many other things besides received information and may close their eyes on problems that are either difficult to grasp or impossible to solve for an individual. Larger emphasis should be paid on practical measures that engage not necessarily the public, but the stakeholders and decision makers of each specific 'problem' (whether they're harmful personal care products or emerging contaminants). Researchers should be brave in organising into lobbyist-like groups and contacting decision-makers when the time is right for each pollution-related problem. We should also have solutions to offer, instead of simply pointing out that some practice, product or form of energy is bad for the environment. Changes in policy are primordial (a good example will be the ban of neonicotinoids by the EU). Besides providing evidence-based information on the negative effect of X on Y, the science community should also take time to influence policy (and this can be done at different levels: from council/county to state).

Theme: Anthropogenic ecosystems

1) Global perspectives that Ripple et al. (2017) do not acknowledge, emerge from this research:

None.

2) Topics that conservation science should study, and how these topics should/could be research?

There was an idea to study humans' role as an apex predator. It was linked to the discourse whether there is anthropogenic ecosystems at all or should humans be consider as an inseparable part of nature. On the other hand, all ecosystems seem to be under humans act, such as pollution, so that we cannot even separate non-anthropogenic ecosystems even we wanted to think about humans as an individual actor separately from nature. Deep down this might be philosophical conflict between different science traditions and might cause interdisciplinary challenges.

3) The role of researchers in the future:

As Ripple et al. (2017) noticed, nature education will encourage the appreciation of nature. In this work it was also adjust that society and scientists have both a critical role to success in the global efforts to conserve. On the contrast, there is also a problem with the ecological relevance when cultural values are affecting our conservation actions. It might be so that the cutest species will be protected more than the species that would ecologically be more important.

Deepening of the qualitative analysis

In order to produce a summary over the content of the thematic discussions, and to double-check the consistency between the original data and the results of the qualitative analysis, a final read-through of the workshop documentation and the above described analytical memos was done by author 1. Here, the discussions' contents were related to the emergent scopes (individual, discipline, and global perspectives, which were connected to the guiding questions of the analytical memos). A representative quotation was selected for every scope under each theme among the written notes from the workshop. The results are shown in table S2.

Table S2. A summary of the discussion themes that emerged from survey comments and were elaborated in the workshop. The quotations shown in the table are examples of individual workshop participants' suggestions on advancing sustainability. The quotations are categorised according to the level of perceived agency in relation to the mentioned sustainability actions, to show the range of individual, discipline, and global perspectives with the workshop data (columns 3-4). Note that many of the quotations indicate connections among the levels of agency; this is further illustrated in Figure 3 of the article.

Discussion theme	Number of respondent comments ^a	The level of perceived agency		
		Individual	Discipline	Global
Transdisciplinary research, governance, and politics	25	'Try to be involving, don't be too judgemental.'	'Be careful not to take multidisciplinary as the goal. It is a tool.'	'There's not one political solution but several ones.'
Education, science communication, and implementation	20	'Get the science out there with science communication.'	'Involve stakeholders throughout the research process.'	'Get kids into nature and let them be inspired.'
Human health and lifestyle	16	'Shift priority from luxury items to necessities or commodities.'	'Encourage online meetings instead of long-distance travel.'	'Less consumption.'
Ethical issues, values, and inequality	12	'In research, don't impose your ('western') views and values.'	'Incorporate the human dimension in conservation research.'	'Global collaboration in tax systems.'
Economy and marketing	9	'Don't support the [current] system!'	'We as researchers need to show the connection between human well-being and biodiversity conservation.'	'Disconnect from the idea of growth.'
Environmental pollution, contamination, and waste	8	'Use more sustainable products if possible.'	'More research on comparing policies: penalties or subsidies?'	'Better environmental awareness globally.'
Anthropogenic ecosystems	5	'Consider the area in which you choose to live, the level of ecological impacts it generates.'	'What is an anthropogenic ecosystem – are there non-anthropogenic ecosystems?'	'Complete separation of humans and nature – impossible.'

^a Number of survey respondents' free-text comments relating to each theme.

Based on the discussion summaries, a set of sustainability steps under the discussion themes was derived. The initial list of steps was scrutinised by all authors, and when a consensus was achieved on which steps should be included, authors 1 and 2 roughly categorised the steps according to their level of reformism / radicalism. The order of the presentation of the steps was further refined by using the leverage points framework (Meadows 1999; Abson et al. 2017), which can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of sustainability interventions according to the systemic impact of the studied interventions. The leverage points framework corresponds to the continuum from reformist to radical action (that range from 'shallow' to 'deep' leverage), and as it is a tool for systems analysis, it allowed for detection of interactions among the identified sustainability actions. This was utilised in ordering of the steps (see Figure 3 in the article). Also, the information on the level of perceived agency (individual – discipline – global) of each step was retained to include the holistic multi-level approach also in the results.

All of the thirteen sustainability actions were perceived as important but differed in their overall ranking. The three most valued actions were: (1) establishing reserves for nature protection, (2) enhancing the use of new green technologies and renewable energy sources, and (3) revising the prevalent economy (table S3).

Table S3. Actions towards sustainability according to the World Scientists' Warning to Humanity: A Second Notice (Ripple et al. 2017), and their prioritisation according to the questionnaire respondents ($n=67$).

Description	Short description	Frequency	Rank
Prioritising the enactment of connected well-funded and well-managed reserves for a significant proportion of the world's terrestrial, marine, freshwater, and aerial habitats.	Reserves	31	1
Devising and promoting new green technologies and massively adopting renewable energy sources while phasing out subsidies to energy production through fossil fuels.	Technologies	27	2
Revising our economy to reduce wealth inequality and ensure that prices, taxation, and incentive systems take into account the real costs which consumption patterns impose on our environment.	Economy	24	3
Maintaining nature's ecosystem services by halting the conversion of forests, grasslands, and other native habitats.	Halt conversion	20	4
Further reducing fertility rates by ensuring that women and men have access to education and voluntary family-planning services, especially where such resources are still lacking.	Fertility	19	5–6
Increasing outdoor nature education for children, as well as the overall engagement of society in the appreciation of nature.	Nature appreciation	19	5–6
Promoting dietary shifts towards mostly plant-based foods.	Diets	16	7
Developing and adopting adequate policy instruments to remedy defaunation, the poaching crisis, and the exploitation and trade of threatened species.	Overexploitation	11	8
Reducing food waste through education and better infrastructure.	Food waste	10	9–10
Estimating a scientifically defensible, sustainable human population size for the long term while rallying nations and leaders to support that vital goal.	Population	10	9–10
Restoring native plant communities at large scales, particularly forest landscapes.	Restoration	8	11
Rewilding regions with native species, especially apex predators, to restore ecological processes and dynamics.	Rewilding	3	12–13
Divesting of monetary investments and purchases to encourage positive environmental change.	Investments	3	12–13

Based on the pairwise comparisons, the respondents gave priorities to a variety of different combinations of actions (figure S2). On average, any two respondents prioritised one shared step, but prioritised two actions differently (respondents dissimilarity was 0.69). We further reflected the heterogeneity among the answers in the co-occurrence analysis, which demonstrated no dominant positive associations between the actions. The majority of the pairwise associations followed a random pattern. However, seven associations occurred less frequently than expected (figure S2; negative associations in yellow colour). In these cases, the differences between the expected and the observed number of co-occurrences varied between 2.9 and 3.7.

The 27 respondents who prioritised promotion of new green technologies and adoption of renewable energy production were unlikely to give another vote to increasing of nature appreciation or reducing fertility rates (in both cases, the expected number of co-occurrences was 7.7 but only 4 cases were observed). Similarly, the 20 respondents who voted for halting land-use conversions in favour of sustained ecosystem services rarely prioritised increasing of nature appreciation (2 observed co-occurrences; 5.7 expected) and reducing of food waste (no co-occurrences; 3 expected). Increasing of nature appreciation was negatively associated also to promotion of plant-based diets (1 co-occurrence; 4.5 expected). The rest of the negative associations were between faunal overexploitation and either establishment of reserves (2 observed co-occurrences; 5.1 expected) or revising the current economy (1 observed co-occurrence; 3.9 expected).

Figure S2. Results of the co-occurrence analysis on the ranking of Ripple et al.'s (2017) actions towards sustainability, based on the pre-workshop survey data. Negative associations (observed co-occurrence rate significantly lower than expected) are shown in yellow. Full descriptions of the actions are given in table S2.

R script (quantitative analysis)

```
# SURVEY ANALYSIS

# Set working directory

setwd("...")

# Load packages

library(cooccur)
library(ggplot2)
library(vegan)

# 1. Pairwise co-occurrence of actions selected as top 3 by participants

# Format data: 1 for selected, 0 for non-selected actions; actions as row names, participants as columns
# Read original data
data1 <- read.table('Survey_answers.txt', header=T, sep='\t')
# Remove participant who graduated before 2018
data1 <- data1[-38,]
# Save participant numbers to be used later as column names
r_names <- data1[,1]
# Delete column with participant numbers
data2 <- as.matrix(data1[, -1])
# Replace missing values with zeros
data2[is.na(data2)] <- 0
# Replace other values as ones
data2[data2 > 0] <- 1
```

```

# Transpose and change column names
data2 <- as.data.frame(t(data2))
colnames(data2) <- r_names

# Analysis: Test for non-random pairwise co-occurrence using function cooccur
# Run the model
model1 <- cooccur(mat=data2, spp_names=T, thresh = F)
# Model results
model1
# Exploration: Model summary
summary(model1)
# Exploration: Results plots
plot(model1)
pair.profile(model1)
obs.v.exp(model1)
# Exploration: All pairwise results, e.g. for Reserves
pair(model1, "Reserves", all=T)
# Save a table with results for all pairs into a dataframe
table1 <- prob.table(model1)

# Plot with all pairs (similar to what plot(model1) draws)
# Create new dataframe with relevant columns
table_pairs <- table1[c('sp1_name', 'sp2_name', 'obs_cooccur', 'exp_cooccur', 'p_lt', 'p_gt')]
# Add a new column indicating whether patterns are significant negative, significant positive, or random
table_pairs$association[table_pairs$obs_cooccur<table_pairs$exp_cooccur & table_pairs$p_lt < 0.05] <- 'negative'
table_pairs$association[table_pairs$obs_cooccur>table_pairs$exp_cooccur & table_pairs$p_gt < 0.05] <- 'positive'
table_pairs$association[is.na(table_pairs$association)] <- 'random'
# Make sure actions and associations are factors and in the desired order (here, same as in the list in Ripple et al.)
table_pairs$sp1_name <- factor(table_pairs$sp1_name, levels = unique(table_pairs$sp1_name))
table_pairs$sp2_name <- factor(table_pairs$sp2_name, levels = unique(table_pairs$sp1_name))
table_pairs <- table_pairs[!is.na(table_pairs$sp2_name),]
table_pairs$association <- factor(table_pairs$association, levels = c('negative', 'random', 'positive'))

# Create plot and save to file
plot1 <- ggplot(table_pairs, aes(x=sp2_name, y=sp1_name)) +
  geom_tile(aes(fill=association), color='white') +
  labs(x="", y="") +
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('gold', 'lightgrey', 'lightblue')) +
  theme(panel.grid.major = element_blank(), panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),
        panel.background = element_blank(), axis.line = element_blank(), axis.ticks = element_blank(),
        axis.text.x=element_text(size=9, color='Black', angle=45, hjust=1), axis.text.y=element_text(size=9,
color='Black'),
        axis.title=element_text(size=9, face='bold'), legend.title=element_blank(), legend.text=element_text(size=9))

jpeg("pairwise_matrix.jpeg", height = 8, width = 14, units = 'cm', res = 600)
plot1
dev.off()

```

```
# 2. Calculate average dissimilarity between top 3s selected by participants
```

```
# Format data: 1 for selected, 0 for non-selected actions; actions as columns, participants as rows
```

```
# Delete column with participant numbers from original data
```

```
data3 <- as.data.frame(data1[, -1])
```

```
# Replace missing values with zeros
```

```
data3[is.na(data3)] <- 0
```

```
# Replace other values as ones
```

```
data3[data3 > 0] <- 1
```

```
# Calculate pairwise dissimilarity matrix with function vegdist
```

```
model2 <- vegdist(data3, method='bray', binary = T, upper=F)
```

```
# Save as matrix
```

```
table2 <- as.matrix(model2)
```

```
# Loop over matrix to calculate sum of pairwise dissimilarities and total number of pairs
```

```
# The same pair is included only once and pairings of participants with themselves are not included
```

```
dist_sum <- 0.0
```

```
n_pairs <- 0.0
```

```
for(i in seq(1,ncol(table2)-1)){
```

```
  for(j in seq(i,nrow(table2))){
```

```
    dist_sum <- dist_sum + table2[j,i]
```

```
    n_pairs <- n_pairs + 1.0
```

```
  }
```

```
}
```

```
# Divide sum by number of pairs to get the average
```

```
dist_sum / n_pairs
```

```
# = 0.6895037, i.e. on average one action is the same and two are different
```

Data (quantitative analysis)

Survey_answers.txt

Participant	Reserves	HaltConversion	Restoration	Rewilding	Overexploitation	Food Waste	Diets	Fertility	NatureAppreciation	Investments	Technologies	Economy	Population
1	1	2								10			
2	1								9			12	
3	1										11	12	
4	1					6	7						
5		2					7				11		
6	1				5				9				
7	1	2	3										
8		2										12	13
9		2					7					12	

10						7	8			11		
11			3			6	8					
12	1			4							12	
13					5				9	11		
14	1										12	13
15							8				12	13
16					5		8	9				
17		2			5		7					
18							7	8		11		
19	1						7				12	
20				4		6			9			
21					5			8		11		
22	1						7	8				
23							7			11	12	
24						6				11		13
25	1	2						8				
26	1	2								11		
27	1		3	4								
28		2			5					11		
29					5	6			9			
30	1								9	11		
31		2					7	8				
32						6	7	8				
33			3					8			12	
34	1	2									12	
35			3							11	12	
36			3					8			12	
37									9	10	12	
38		2						8		11		
39	1								9		12	
40	1						7	8				
41	1							8	9			
42	1							8		11		
43								8	9			13
44							7	8			12	
45		2							9			13
46			3		5						12	
47	1								9	11		
48						6				11	12	
49	1	2								11		
50	1					6			9			
51						6				11	12	
52		2								11	12	
53							7		9		12	
54					5					11		13
55		2						8			12	
56	1									11		13

57		2									11	12	
58	1						8	9					
59	1	2									11		
60	1							9				12	
61		2					7				11		
62		2						9					13
63	1	2	3										
64	1										11		13
65					5					10	11		
66	1							9			11		
67	1					6					11		
68	1				5		7						

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